

MINDSITE: Empowering Adolescents to Sidestep Self-Diagnosis and its Social Relation

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Abstract

Low mental health literacy, the rising tendency of self-diagnosis, and its associated stigmatization have become significant challenges among adolescents in the digital era. With the widespread accessibility of online mental health information, many adolescents interpret symptoms independently without adequate understanding, which may lead not only to misdiagnosis but also to the development of both self-stigma and public stigma. While Indonesia has identified mental health as a national priority, the implementation of effective literacy-based interventions remains limited. This study aims to examine the relationship between self-diagnosis tendencies and stigmatization, as well as to evaluate the effectiveness of MINDSITE (Website-based Mindfulness) in improving mental health literacy among adolescents. A pre-experimental design (one-group pre-test and post-test) was employed using an adapted Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) questionnaire. A total of 52 adolescents aged 15–18 participated by engaging with MINDSITE, a platform integrating mindful reading and structured mental health content based on DSM-5. The findings revealed a strong positive correlation between self-diagnosis and stigmatization ($r = 0.887$), indicating that higher tendencies of self-diagnosis are associated with increased stigmatizing attitudes. In addition, improvements were observed across five of six MHLS indicators, including recognition of mental disorders, risk factors, causes, and appropriate help-seeking behavior. A paired t-test analysis demonstrated a significant increase in mental health literacy following the intervention ($t = -12.790$; $p < 0.05$). These results suggest that MINDSITE is a viable and accessible approach to enhancing mental health literacy while simultaneously reducing the risks of self-diagnosis and stigmatization among adolescents.

Keyword: *Mental health literacy, Adolescents, MINDSITE therapy*

Introduction

Adolescence is a critical time for the development of an individual's identity which is marked by significant changes in psychological, social, and emotional growth [4]. During this period, adolescents are especially vulnerable to mental health problems which are increasingly influenced by constant access to the vast amount of information available online [12]. According to Data Reportal, internet users are growing rapidly by 1.8 percent, bringing the total global internet users to 5.35 billion by early 2024 and making the internet a space for users to express their feelings [9].

However, with the open access to the internet, self-diagnosis is often done because of curiosity related to the symptoms of the disease experienced and compared with existing references [6]. The trend of self-diagnosis based on general information provided on social media can lead to inappropriate treatment, thus worsening mental health. Furthermore, this self-diagnosis action has an impact on society, one of which is in the form of stigmatizing behavior. [1] [10].

Goffman stated that the act of self-diagnosis can lead to a "spoiled identity," where the individual's sense of self is tainted by the stigma associated with their self-diagnosed condition, as stigma is a profound social phenomenon where individuals are discredited based on attributes that deviate from societal norms [5].

This stigma can manifest both as public stigma, which involves the reaction that the general population has to people with mental illness, and self-stigma is the prejudice which people with mental illness turn against themselves [3].

One of the strategies to challenge stigmatic attitudes is by education. Jorm's previous research stated that knowledge is important for changing stigmatic beliefs towards people with mental illness [2]. It can decrease prejudice against mental health patients, raise awareness of mental disorders, and prevent stigmatizing labeling [2]. While stigma impedes people from seeking and receiving professional treatment, improving knowledge of mental health might offer a solution [8]. By looking at this phenomenon, a solution is offered to reduce the tendency of self-diagnosis by improving mental health literacy through MINDSITE,

an adoption of the Mindfulness method using a website containing the Mindful Reading and mental health literature based on DSM-5 (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders). Adolescents tend to seek information that is considered interesting without understanding it comprehensively [7]. Therefore, MINDSITE is expected to be an effective approach to reduce the trend of self-diagnosis by increasing mental health literacy.

Research Method

Research Objective and Benefits

This study aims to determine whether information on the internet, especially those related to mental issues, can influence an individual's tendency to self-diagnose and whether there is a relationship between self-diagnose and stigmatizing behavior. Therefore, this study initiated MINDSITE as a solution to address the issue. It is hoped that MINDSITE will be a method that is easily accessible anywhere and anytime to reduce the tendency of adolescents to self-diagnose, thereby reducing the associated stigmatizing behavior.

Research Question

The research question of this study is: "How is the relationship between individual identity construction related to self-diagnosis and the tendency towards stigmatization of mental health issues?"

Research Methodology

1. Initial stage of research

- a) Initial assessment: includes literature study, formulation of research question, benefits and aims of this research.
- b) The Research Method used was Correlational research design with quantitative methods. There are 2 variables that are measured: self-diagnose tendency and stigmatization tendency.
- c) Arranging instruments were done by using the 4-point Likert scale. The set of questions to measure self-diagnose tendency is based on previous paper [1]. Whereas stigmatization tendency questions are taken from Community Attitudes Toward the Mentally ill (CAMI) scale [13]. Statements in the questionnaire are then adapted and customized as needed. The questionnaire was tested using Anates item analysis software and produced a validity value = 0.80 and test reliability value = 0.89.

To ensure a structured and measurable assessment, the research variables were operationalized into specific indicators.

Table 1 – Indicators of Self-Diagnose

Research Variable	No.	Indicator	Instrument Item Number
Self-Diagnose	1.1	Perception of Mental Health Issues	1, 2, 8
	1.2	Identification with Symptoms Discussed in Internet	3, 4, 9
	1.3	Reinforcement of Self-Diagnosis Through Repeated Exposure	5, 10, 11
	1.4	Perceived Effectiveness of Social Media Mental Health Content	6, 12, 13
	1.5	Reliance on Social Media for Mental Health Self-Diagnosis	7, 14, 15

Table 2 – Indicators of Stigmatization

Research Variable	No.	Indicator	Instrument Item Number
Stigmatization	2.1	Authoritarianism	1-7
	2.2	Benevolence	8-13
	2.3	Social Restrictiveness	14-19
	2.4	Community Mental Health Ideology	20-25

These dimensions are also consistent with the conceptual framework of stigma proposed by Corrigan and Watson [3], which categorizes stigma into stereotypes (cognitive), prejudice (affective), and discrimination (behavioral).

2. Conducting stage of research,

Starting with identifying the subjects, namely adolescents aged 15-18 years, then distributing the questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire in the form of Likert scale statements are then given an assessment using the following formula:

Image 1 - Respondent data scoring calculation

Image 2 – MINDSITE Interface

Respondents were then given a treatment, namely MINDSITE which can be accessed from: <https://sites.google.com/view/mindsitetherapy/beranda>. MINDSITE is an adoption of website-based Mindfulness method which contains Mindful Reading, mental health literacy based on DSM-5, Mindfulness videos and articles inviting socialization with people with mental disorders and consulting with professionals.

3. Final research stage, in which the data was processed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS to see the correlation between the two variables. At this stage, the results of the data that have been analyzed will be processed and presented in the form of graphs and tables, then complement the results of the analysis with a description.

Result and Analysis

Respondents collected in this study involved 100 adolescents, consisting of 60 girls and 40 boys:

Image 3 - Correlation between self-diagnosis and stigmatization

The graph shows a very strong positive correlation between self-diagnosis and stigmatization with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.887$. A positive r value indicates that, if the tendency of adolescents to self-diagnose is high, the tendency of stigmatization will also increase. This finding is also in line with previous research which stated that a diagnosis can negatively affect a young person's social identity by exposing them to stigma, and some young people feel their diagnosis invalidates them in others' eyes and leads to social alienation and interpersonal strife [11].

This research also revealed that adolescents had experienced both self-stigma and/or public stigma as detailed below:

Image 4 - Forms of self-stigma and public-stigma

Self-stigma most often occurs in the form of prejudice, which is agreement with beliefs, negative emotional reactions (e.g., low self-esteem, low self-efficacy). Whereas public stigma most often occurs in the form of discrimination, which is a behavior response to prejudice (e.g., avoidance, withhold employment and housing opportunities, withhold help) [3]. This research also shows the tendency towards self-diagnosis increases when the intensity of internet use to access mental health content is also high, which is in line with previous studies which stated that self-diagnosis is significantly correlated with the intensity of internet use [14].

Image 5 – Relationship between internet intensity and self-diagnose

Therefore, MINDSITE can be the right solution proposed to reduce the tendency of adolescents to self-diagnose with the mindfulness method and mental health literacy based on DSM-5. To see the effectiveness of MINDSITE, the researcher used a paired sample t-test with alpha set = 0.05 which was processed in SPSS and the following results were obtained:

Image 8 - Statistical data results comparing pre-test and post-test

The comparison of statistical results between pre-test and post-test assessments has a highly significant difference, proven by the p value <0.001, which explains that MINDSITE treatment has had a positive impact on increasing mental health literacy in adolescents so that it can be an alternative solution to reduce the tendency of self-diagnosis.

What makes these findings particularly important is how closely they reflect the reality of adolescents growing up in a fully digital environment. Today's teenagers are not just passive consumers of information—they are constantly navigating an overwhelming stream of mental health content, much of which is simplified, fragmented, or even misleading. As highlighted in previous studies, limited mental health literacy can make adolescents more vulnerable to misinterpreting symptoms and prematurely labelling themselves without proper clinical understanding [2].

In this context, self-diagnosis is not merely an individual behaviour, but part of a broader digital culture where mental health terms are widely circulated without sufficient explanation. Global reports, including those from the World Health Organization, emphasize that improving mental health literacy is one of the most effective strategies to reduce stigma and encourage appropriate help-seeking behaviour. When adolescents develop a more accurate understanding of mental health, they are less likely to rely on assumptions and more likely to seek professional support [8].

The strong relationship between self-diagnosis and stigmatization found in this study also reflects a deeper psychological process. When individuals adopt diagnostic labels without adequate understanding, these labels can shape their self-concept and influence how they perceive others' judgments. This aligns with classical theories of stigma, where individuals experience both social discrediting and internalized negative beliefs [3][5]. In the digital era, this process is further amplified by repeated exposure to similar content and social comparison, which can reinforce both self-stigma and public stigma.

This is where MINDSITE becomes particularly relevant. Rather than simply providing information, it integrates structured mental health knowledge with mindfulness-based approaches, enabling adolescents to pause, reflect, and interpret information more critically. Recent research suggests that combining psychoeducation with mindfulness can significantly improve not only knowledge but also emotional regulation and decision-making in adolescents [2][8].

Therefore, the effectiveness of MINDSITE extends beyond the statistical improvement shown in this study. It represents an adaptive response to the challenges of modern digital life, where the ability to critically process information and maintain a balanced self-perception is essential. By addressing both cognitive understanding and emotional awareness, MINDSITE offers a more holistic approach to reducing self-diagnosis tendencies and the stigmatization that often follows.

Conclusion

Open access to the internet, especially content related to mental health, has influenced adolescents' lives. The trend of self-diagnosis based on information that adolescents get on the internet is increasing and influencing the way they judge themselves and others. This research found that self-diagnose behavior has a very strong positive correlation with stigmatization behavior, both self-stigma and public stigma. As a result, MINDSITE is relevant to be offered as a solution to overcome the issue of self-diagnose by increasing mental health literacy, thus reducing the tendency of stigmatization.

Future Work

This study has provided some intriguing findings about the correlation between self-diagnose tendencies and stigmatization in adolescents. However, this study still has some shortcomings in terms of detail, especially regarding the age group which is only limited to adolescents. Future research should aim to expand the scope of this study by including more diverse respondents, such as adults and individuals from different socio-demographic backgrounds in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding. This research can also be a reference for further research in providing similar treatment and its development related to the issues of self-diagnosis and stigmatization.

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